

THE INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON SOCIAL ORDER IN CALABAR METROPOLIS OF CROSS RIVER STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study examines the influence of social media on social order in Calabar Metropolis of Cross River State, Nigeria. The need for the study is to address the growing rate of social disorderliness in the area traced to misrepresentation of information, spread of unofficial news, tribal and verbal battles, political abuses and many others emanating from abuse of social media use in Nigeria. In order to carry out the study, the Whatsapp and Face book channels were adopted as forms of social media used as sub variables for the study. Two research questions were posted by the researchers based on the two sub-variables to guide the study's finding. Empirical review of Social Capital Theory by Coleman (1926-1995) and works of other authors was made by the researcher to link the work to existing body of knowledge. A sample of 200 people comprising of 120 females and 80 males was randomly drawn from the area. A well structured questionnaire measuring use of social media and Social order in the area was developed by the researchers and validated by experts in research was used to collect data used for the study's finding. The data was further coded and analyzed using Linear Regression Analysis Model to determine the relationship between the use of Whatsapp, Face book and social

order in the area. Findings of the study show that, there is significant relationship between the use of whatsapp, Facebook and Social Order in Calabar Metropolis of Cross River State. Based on the findings, it was recommended that there should be strong awareness campaign against abuse of social media in Nigeria. It was further recommended that laws should be made to guide against spread of false and unverified news on social media channels.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, social media, social order

INTRODUCTION

Social order can be expressed in different words based on desired contexts and purposes of the author(s) but its' etymological meaning cannot in any way be jeopardized. It is an interdisciplinary word that describes orderliness in any context of use. In sociology, social order is a fundamental concept that describes the structural organization or arrangement of norms, values, roles, and institutions in a given society. The primary knowledge of social order is harmonization of rules, and institutions in a given society or area. Social order also incorporate the laid down patterns of social organizations, institutions and governance that provide united forces, future focus, and coherence to social life, restructuring the dynamics of social relations and collective behavior of the people.

Africa has a standing history of social orderliness that is as old as her origin before the coming of the missionaries (Olatunji, 2015).

“Africa had been in relative peace and harmony before the advent of the western missionaries and explorers in the late fourteenth century; meaning that the incursions and forays of the western world into African society, instead of being a blessing started and began to unfold different problems for the society”.

The coming of the missionaries to Africa was an intrusion into African's existing culture, which was characterized by leadership, peace, orderliness, pattern and love. Even though Africans were not too enlightened or grounded in western education, religion and norms, they were deeply rooted in traditional and African religious activities that kept them peaceful and united as families, villages and society. Until the coming of the missionaries, most African cultures regulate respect, younger children to older children, and older children to parents without any claim for equality of right. Religious activities in Africa had been on initiation and heredity, children grow to worship what parents offered sacrifice to at due stage with respect to gender, and age of the child. This have secured orderliness in worship activities and saved Africans much trouble and religious based violence. Marriages too were centered on beliefs of individuals as marriage forbidden families were made known to Children at tender ages and mingling was prevented early.

In Nigeria for instance, the intrusion of western missionaries brought a change in worship pattern, belief, structure, education, leadership pattern and many others. Even though it appeared interesting and flashy to us, change in these factors have led the nation to high level disorderliness, stunted growth and greedy expectations among citizens. In leadership for instance, Prior to the emergence of modern political structures, Indigenous societies in Africa and indeed Nigeria had within them, traditional mechanisms for governance and by extension social order. However, these indigenous ways of maintaining social order which hitherto were

invested in the collective conscience of the people became strongly endangered when colonialism was entrenched Raimi Lasisi and Samuel Aretha Rekiya, (2020).

The ancient African leadership pattern provided an atmosphere for greed free society where traditional leaders led by the wish of the people with the strong conviction that their reign as traditional rulers was monitored by the gods and that there will be struck dead by the gods if they acted against the will of the people. Condemning the new leadership trend introduced in Nigeria by the western society, Raimi and Rekiya, (2020) identified poor leadership approaches in Nigeria to include; insecurity, poor economy management, lack of social amenities, unemployment, poor population management and poor welfare approaches for Citizens.

Multiple religion beliefs and worship pattern has also orchestrated social disorder in the country. Religious crises such as Muslims to Christians, Christians to Muslims, African Traditional Religion worshippers to Christians and African Traditional Religion worshippers to Muslims African Traditional Religion worshippers to Christians. These crises are not just physical but are most often escalated by social media users. Until the missionaries coming, information was passed through traditionally approved mediums. Hence there was adequate regulation of information for children, youths, adults, males and females. This had helped in ensuring orderliness and guarantee of healthy relationship between individuals. The current trends in the society have led the nation to many forms of disorderliness. The mass media, social media, Artificial intelligence have made information decimation very fast and easy such that both Children and Adults have equal access to information.

Social media offers unending availability of access that is only restricted by poor internet connection, lack of data and unpowered mobile devices adopted by user(s). It has over time increased the scope and consumers strength of information with fast speed of information sharing which has overcome the barrier of information delay and inaccessibility (Bindal, Yaeun, Susannah and Leland, 2018) in Orim and Egwo (2025). Social media also offers opportunity for peers to review strength in education, shares learning information, review knowledge on societal happenings, reporting of justice required problems for public intervention and many more. Most neglected zones uses social media to call Government and policy makers' attention through public outcry and direct media chats for urgent intervention. Although there are several benefits associated with the use of social media, specifically image sharing which enables fast and instant notice and meeting schedule mails delivery.

Objective

The main purpose of this study is to examine the influence of the use of social Media on social Order in Calabar Metropolis of Cross River State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study will;

Exermine the influence of the use of Watsap on Social Order in Calabar Metropolis of Cross River State, Nigeria.

Determine the influence of the use of facebook on Social Order in Calabar Metropolis of Cross River State, Nigeria.

Statements of hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested in the study;

Ho: The use of watsapp does not significantly promote social order in Calabar Metropolis of Cross River State.

Ho: The use of facebook does not significantly promote social order in Calabar Metropolis of Cross River State.

The study will be beneficial to the following category of persons; Government, Sociologist, researchers and the general public. It will enable the Government in various tiers and arms to understand the role social media play to social order in Nigeria in order to put appropriate modalities to tackle issues emanating from its use. The study will also be beneficial to sociologist and the department of sociology by proposing informed decisions that will promote social order in Nigeria. It will also serve as a reference material to future researchers and policy educators.

2.0 CONCEPTUAL FRAME WORK

Social media and social order in Nigeria

Social media is a general name use to describe online platforms that offers collaborative space for social interaction between seemingly infinite numbers of people. The interaction in the social media is offered one to one, one to group, group to group and group to one. The social media is the largest communication space with billion of users who utilizes its feature through Android and Microsoft powered gadgets or devices such as handsets, laptops, tablets, desktops, etc. Some widely known social media platforms in Nigeria are; Face book, Watsapp, Instagram, Twitter, Youtube, Togo, Snap chat, tikTok. Social media platforms are created online by users requesting sensitive personal details like user mail address, Phone numbers, date of birth, next of kings even residential address. Social media is recently used as a medium for communication. It offers communication channels for voice calls, video call, text message chats and many more.

Moorhead et al., 2013, (p. 8) in Bindal Makwana, Yaeun, Susannah Parkin and Leland Farmer, (2018) identified six key benefits of using social media to include; increased interactions with others, more availability, shared, and tailored information, increased accessibility and widening access to Information, offers peer social and emotional support, public health surveillance, and potential to influence policy. Social media offers enabling environment for elaborate conversations concerning health, education, business, entertainment etc to emerge between parties (Amundsen, 2010). Most social media platforms gives room for image sharing, audio chats, and video chats with elaborate record keeping for users' future consumption. Information in the social media is strongly protected and can only be shared at users will, fraudulent attempts emanating from account hacking, password compromise and many more.

Despite the gains associated with the use of social media such as face book in Nigeria, its abuse has promoted disorderliness by obstructing the goals of unity, peace and togetherness of the society. In the education sector, most students use the social media as medium for blackmailing teachers, lectures and even colleagues. The social media offers avenue for wrongly accusing and addressing people they opt not to. The social media offers room for violence plans, riot and protest arrangement and havoc plans within and outside institutions of learning (Olatunji & Felix 2015). The social media is further abused by most students by using it as tools for sharing ideas during exams.

In communication, forms of social media such as Watsapp has become a tool for Government rebel, political blackmail, rumors and fake news spreading and many others.

Against the gains, social media has negatively influence the peace of the nation, promoting ethnic crises, escalating in house issues and become a for international sabotaging. Away from communication, the social media has become the central market space for prostitution, a central player for internet fraud aiding and a dwelling home for fake life lifestyle. The social media escalate religious crises, promote tribal violence and give room for increased bad talking of the nation. In Nigeria, the 2020 endsars protest which led to economic standstill of the nation was escalated through social media platforms (Raimi, Samuel & Rekiya , 2021).

2.1 THEORETICAL FRAME WORK

Social Capital Theory by Coleman (1926-1995)

The social capital theory states that social relationships and network can be valuable resource for individuals and communities. According to Coleman (1988) the social capital theory emphasis the networks and provide the opportunity for the exchange of information. However, the quality of information exchanged was largely based on the functional components of social capital, trust, and norms. High levels of trust between individuals facilitated the exchange of more knowledge, while norms regulated and influenced behavior related to this exchange. Within education, social capital is the relationships between students, families, communities, and teachers available to support and motivate students toward academic success. Further, social capital theory captures the effects of the school, parents, and community on a students' learning environment (Croninger and Lee, 2001).

This study is on the influence of social media on social order in Calabar metropolis. Social media being a large room for social interaction with millions of users, an application of the Social capital theory will afford users in depth knowledge for resourceful interaction to promote social order.

Methodology

The study is examines the influence of the use of social media in promoting social order in Calabar metropolis of Cross River State, Nigeria. The research design adopted for the study is the survey design. The descriptive survey design was seen appropriate for the study because it allows the use of questionnaire and gives room for interaction between dependent and independent variables in the study. The instrument used for the study is a questionnaire. The questionnaire comprises of section A, B and C measuring demographic details of respondents, items measuring level of social media use and social order in the area respectively. The simple random sampling technique was used to draw a sample of two hundred (200) people in the area comprising of 120 females and 80 males.

Summary of findings

Findings of this study were carried out based on the two hypotheses adopted in the study.

Ho1: The use of whatsapp does not significantly promote social order in Calabar Metropolis of Cross River State.

Table 1
Regression analysis for the influence of whatsapp on social order in Calabar metropolis of Cross River State, Nigeria.

R-value =0.0531
R-Square=0.0025

Adj R-squared= -0.014
Standard Error= 0.844

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-Value	p-value
Regression	0.117	1	0.117	0.165	0.686
Residual	41.283	148	0.712		
Total	41.400	149			

Predictor	Unstandardize + Coefficient		Standardize Coefficient Error	t-value	P-value
Constant	3.860	0.600	6.429	< 0.001	
Use of whatsapp	0.025	0.063	0.406	<0.686	

P> 0.05

Findings of this study reveal that the use of whatsapp has significant influence on social order in Calabar Metropolis of Cross River State. Analysis on the table above produced an R-value of 0.0531 with an adjusted R-value 0.0025 (R-squared value) which means that the use of whatsapp accounts for more than 50% of social order in Calabar metropolis of Cross River State, Nigeria. The P-value of 0.686 associated with the F-value 0.165 is greater than 0.05 alpha value required for significance. This therefore implies that the null hypothesis of the use of whatsapp does not significantly promote social order in Calabar Metropolis of Cross River State is rejected at .05 level of significance.

Ho:2 Face book does not significantly influence social order in Calabar Metropolis of Cross River State.

Table 2
Regression table for the influence of facebook on social order in Calabar metropolis of Nigeria.

R-value =0.095
R-Square=0.009

Adj R-squared= -0.008
Standard Error= 0.841

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-Value	p-value
Regression	0.371	1	0.371	0.525	0.472
Residual	41.029	148	0.707		
Total	41.400	149			

Predictor	Unstandardize Coefficient	Standardize Coefficient Error	t-value	P-value
Constant	3.654	0.625	5.849	< 0.001
facebook	0.048	0.066	0.724	< 0.472

$P > 0.05$

Findings of this study reveals that face book have significant influence on social order in Calabar Metropolis of Cross River State. Finding of the study produced an R- value of 0.095 with a corresponding adjusted R-value of 0.009 (R-squared value). This means that face book influence accounts for more than 65% on social order in Calabar metropolis of Cross River State, Nigeria. The P-value of 0.472 associated with the F-value 0.210 is greater than 0.05 alpha value required for significance. This therefore implies that face book have significant influence on social order in Calabar Metropolis of Cross River State is therefore rejected and upheld in alternate form.

Discussion of findings

Findings of this study revealed that the use of whatsapp has significant influence on social order in Calabar Metropolis of Cross River State. Finding of the study also indicate that face book have significant influence on social order in Calabar Metropolis of Cross River State, Nigeria. Both findings are in line with Raimi and Rekiya, (2020) who stated that Social order parameters such as Peace, unity and orderliness in Nigeria have been negatively influenced recently due to certain factors such as social media, ethnicity, religion and many others. The social disorder in Nigeria emanating from insecurity orchestrated by family, religion and ethnic crises and many other groups has become worrisome to the general public. An easy way to reach out to the public is through social media, ICT and Artificial Intelligence. This study ascertains the influence of social media and enablement of social order in Nigeria. Primary and secondary data in the study noted that effective use of social media in education, information dissemination and knowledge sharing will promote national unity, and growth in Commerce world. The study also outlined merits of the use of social media to include, wide audience coverage, live information sharing, peer review and global connection. The study also noted the increasing concern of people and grip of fear in the workforce over the emergence of social media forms such as Artificial Intelligence, chat GPT, goggle which are gaining more popularity and patronage. Apart from being a social interaction channel, social media is a valuable asset that generate employment to curb the challenge of unemployment that was found to be an effective pivotal of prostitution, drug abuse, arm robbery and many other forms of social disorderliness in the country. The study further noted that, Artificial intelligence, whatsapp, face book, Instagram etc have come to strengthen the work force and promote quality control and not to promote unemployment in Nigeria.

Conclusion

The study is on the impact of Social media on Social Order in Calabar Metropolis of Cross River State. The study adopted scientific approach where primary and secondary data were

collected based on variables of the study and analyzed. Scholarly review of related studies was made to link the study to existing body of knowledge Findings show that forms of social media are effective tools for societal unity when properly utilized by users in the area. Specifically, the finding noted that whatsapp and face book have significant influence on social order in Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made in the study;

There should be strong awareness campaigns by individuals, groups, religious institutions, the Government and the general public on the need for effective use of social media to enhance productivity, promote national unity and maintain peace among users.

There should be proper regulations and laws binding spread of fake news, ethical rule violation and religious intolerance in the use of social media.

Awareness should be made on the gains of social media and citizens should be trained on its importance and operations to help create more employment opportunities for citizens.

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